

A Complete Approach for Specifying Liveness Properties of the I/O Behavior of Imperative Programs

Bart Jacobs

KU Leuven, Dept. Comp. Sci., imec-DistriNet Research Group

`bart.jacobs@cs.kuleuven.be`

Abstract

At ISoLA 2020 we proposed an approach for specifying liveness properties of the interactive (I/O) behavior of imperative programs in a Hoare logic. In this note, we show that this approach is complete, in that it can express any liveness property.

At ISoLA 2020 [1] we proposed an approach for specifying liveness properties of the interactive (I/O) behavior of imperative programs in a Hoare logic. In this approach, the problem of verifying a liveness property is reduced to the problem of verifying a termination property, or rather, a family of termination properties. For example, to verify that a server always eventually responds to each request, we verify, for each k , that the server terminates, assuming that responding to the k 'th request abruptly terminates program execution. Any total correctness logic can be used to verify such termination properties.

In this brief note, we show that this approach is complete: any liveness property \mathbb{P} can be translated into such a family of termination properties. More formally, we show that for any set \mathbb{P} of infinite traces there exists a family $(\mathbb{P}_i)_{i \in I}$ of sets \mathbb{P}_i of finite traces such that

$$\mathbb{P} = \{\vec{c} \mid \forall i \in I. \exists \bar{c} \in \mathbb{P}_i. \bar{c} \prec \vec{c}\} \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{c} \prec \vec{c}$ denotes that finite trace \bar{c} is a prefix of infinite trace \vec{c} . Each such set \mathbb{P}_i can be seen as a termination property, if we imagine that as soon as the program's trace of I/O actions performed so far matches one of the elements of \mathbb{P}_i , program execution terminates.

The proof is easy: we simply take $I = \{\vec{c} \mid \vec{c} \notin \mathbb{P}\}$ and $\mathbb{P}_{\vec{c}} = \{\bar{c} \mid \bar{c} \not\prec \vec{c}\}$. That is, in order to prove that the program satisfies liveness property \mathbb{P} , it is sufficient to prove, for every infinite trace \vec{c} that does not satisfy \mathbb{P} , that the program's I/O behavior eventually diverges from \vec{c} . It is easy to see that Equation 1 holds: indeed, we have

$$\forall \vec{c}' \in \mathbb{P}. \forall \vec{c} \notin \mathbb{P}. \exists \bar{c} \not\prec \vec{c}. \bar{c} \prec \vec{c}'$$

and

$$\forall \vec{c}'. (\forall \vec{c} \notin \mathbb{P}. \exists \vec{c} \not\prec \vec{c}. \vec{c} \prec \vec{c}') \Rightarrow \vec{c}' \in \mathbb{P}$$

We now apply the approach to an example. Let \mathbb{P} be the property that the program eventually always prints the letter `y`. To verify this property, it is sufficient to verify, for every trace \vec{c} in which always eventually a character different from `y` is printed, that the program eventually diverges from that trace. Consider a program that first prints `Hello` and then goes into an infinite loop printing `y`. By $\vec{c} \notin \mathbb{P}$, there exists a $k > 5$ such that $\vec{c}_k \neq y$. Termination of the loop can therefore be proven using k as a loop measure.

Note: in our ISoLA 2020 paper [1], we introduced *ghost actions* to specify “eventually always” properties such as the example property above. In this note, we have shown that ghost actions are not necessary for specifying these or any other liveness properties.

In this note, we did not consider input. However, input can be dealt with easily by fixing it in advance. In other words, to prove that a program p satisfies a property \mathbb{P} , it is sufficient to prove, for every input trace \vec{c} , that p satisfies \mathbb{P} assuming that the input is exactly \vec{c} . This corresponds to making the input available to the proof as a *prophecy variable*.

References

- [1] Bart Jacobs. Modular verification of liveness properties of the I/O behavior of imperative programs. In Proc. ISoLA, LNCS 12476, Springer, 2020.